

INTERNATIONAL UNION OF
PURE AND APPLIED PHYSICS

POSITION AT 1st NOVEMBER 1951
REPORT OF THE
SEVENTH GENERAL ASSEMBLY (1951)

Secretary Office :
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U.I.P.4

*La version française de ce rapport général
ne semble pas disponible ...*

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Union of Pure and Applied Physics receives generous help from United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural organization (U. N. E. S. C. O.) as regards its meetings and publications.

INTERNATIONAL UNION OF PURE AND APPLIED PHYSICS

I. — EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE

(In office until the end of the next General Assembly.)

President of the Union :

Professor M. N. F. MOTT, Physics Laboratory, Royal Fort, Bristol, U. K.

Vice-Presidents :

Messrs.

- E. AMALDI, Inst. « Guglielmo Marconi », Rome (Italy).
- G. BORELIUS, Inst. för Fysik, Kungl. Tekniska Högskolan, Stockholm 26 (Sweden).
- J. HEYROVSKY, Central Inst. of Polarography, Opletova 5, Prague II (Czechoslovakia).
- P. HÜBER, Phys. Anstalt der Universität, Klingelbergstr. 82, Basel (Switzerland).
- K. S. KRISHNAN, Nat. Physical Laboratory, New-Delhi (India).
- M. L. OLIPHANT, National University, Canberra (Australia).
- J. C. SLATER, Mass. Inst. of Technology, Cambridge, Mass. (U. S. A.).
- J. A. WHEELER, Palmer Physical Lab., Princeton, N. J. (U. S. A.).

Former Presidents :

Messrs.

- R. A. MILLIKAN, California Inst. of Technology, Pasadena (U. S. A.).
- M. SIEGBAHN, Nobel Inst. för Fysik, Stockholm (Sweden).
- H. A. KRAMERS, Poelgeesterweg 2, Oegsgeest, Leiden (Netherlands).

Secretary General :

P. FLEURY, 3, boulevard Pasteur, Paris xv^e, France.

N. B. — Correspondence concerning the general work of the Union and receipts and expenditure must be sent or communicated to the Secretary General.

Subscriptions must be paid, preferably in dollars to the account of the Union, c/o Brown Bros., Harriman & Co., New-York, or by cheque to be sent to the Secretary General of the Union.

For the work of the *Commissions*, apply to the appointed Secretary (see pages 6 to 6).

II. — WORK OF THE UNION

1. The work of the International Union of Physics, from its foundation on 1922-1923 until 1947, was summarized in two earlier publications (U. I. P. 1 & 2). We would merely mention here all that the Union owes to its former President, Sir William BRAGG (1922-1931) and to Henri ABRAHAM, who was Secretary General from the beginning until his tragic death (1943).

Under its Statutes (article 2), the Union emanates from the National Committees of Physics in the various member States (see para III). At each General Assembly, delegates of these Committees take decisions with regard to the Union's work, elect the officers and set up the various Commissions (see paras. IV and V). The General Assemblies have been held in Brussels (1923 and 1925), Paris (1931), London (1934), Paris (1947), Amsterdam (1948) and Copenhagen (1951).

In the intervals between General Assemblies urgent decisions are taken by the President and the Executive Committee.

2. The Union of Physics is federated in the *International Council of Scientific Unions*, together with the Unions of Astronomy, Biological Science, Pure and Applied Chemistry, Crystallography, Geodesy and Geophysics, Geography, History of Science, theoretical and Applied Mechanics, and Radio-Science. This Council¹, whose present President is Professor A. von MURALT, in Bern, with Professor F. M. J. STRATTON (Gonville and Caius College, Cambridge, U. K.) as Secretary General, co-ordinates the work of these Unions and administers their Joint Commissions (see below). Its last General Assembly was held in Amsterdam in September 1952. The Council publishes monthly information bulletins, extracts from which are contained in our Union's circulars.

In 1946 the Council of Scientific Unions concluded an agreement with Unesco (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 19, avenue Kléber, Paris XVI^e).

Under this agreement, the Scientific Unions can obtain considerable subventions from Unesco through I. C. S. U., with no loss of independence. Subventions to our Unions, including supplementary grants and authorized carry forward transfers, have been expended as follows: \$ 15,908 in 1947, \$ 16,040 in 1948, \$ 16,214 in 1949 and 16,561 in 1950; and the sum available for 1951 is \$ 16,762.

There is an office for liaison between I. C. S. U. and Unesco, under the direction of Dr. R. FRASER, (formerly under the direction of Dr. Establier), with headquarters in Unesco House. It ensures that information is exchanged in the most effective way.

3. These subventions aided towards the organization between 1947 and 1950 of 21 meetings of Commissions or Symposia (see page 3), which were announced as early as possible and have been reported upon. They also helped to provide 18 fellowships for journey in connexion with work involving international collaboration and to permit of the preparation and dissemination of numerous publications mention of which will be made below.

The Union once more expresses its sincere thanks for this valuable assistance, not only to those who have provided it, but also to those who have laboured to obtain it by shewing that it is well calculated to serve Unesco's essential purposes. In this latter respect, scientists must be permanently active in every country.

Meetings organized from 1947 to 1951 by or in collaboration with the Union of Physics and with Unesco's support¹.

1947	January	Paris	<i>5th General Assembly.</i>
	June	Prague.	International Commission on Optics. Preparatory meeting (Dr J. HRDLICKA).
	July	London	S. U. N., Thermodynamics quantities and symbols, Physico-chemical Data Commissions.
	October	Cracow	<i>Symposium</i> (and commission) on Cosmic Rays (Prof. J. WEYSSENHOFF).
1948	January	Brussels	<i>Symposium</i> (and Commission) on Thermodynamics (Prof. I. PRIGOGINE).
	July	Amsterdam	<i>6th General Assembly</i> — S. U. N., very Low Temperatures, Radioactivity commissions.
	July	Amsterdam	<i>Symposium</i> on the Physics of Metals (Prof. C. J. GORTER).
	July	Delft	International Commission on Optics — 1st Session (Prof. A. C. S. van HEEL).
	November	Paris	<i>Symposium</i> on Cryomagnetic Phenomena, Interaction between X-rays and Matter, Large Molecules in Solution.
1949	May	Florence.	<i>Executive Committee.</i>
	May	Florence.	<i>Symposium</i> on Statistical Mechanics (Prof. H. A. KRAMERS and G. POLYANI).
	June	Paris	<i>Commission</i> on Publications.
	September	Basel	<i>Symposium</i> on nuclear physics (Prof. P. HUBER).
		✓ Como	<i>Symposium</i> on the physics on Cosmic Rays (Prof. G. POLYANI).
		✓ Cambridge (Mass.)	<i>Symposium</i> on the Physics of Very Low Temperatures (Prof. J. C. SLATER).
1950	June	✓ Rome	<i>Symposium</i> on Ultra-acoustics (Prof. GIACOMONI).
	July	✓ Reading.	<i>Symposium</i> on Semi-conductors (Prof. MOTT and DITCHBURN).
	July	London	International Commission on Optics — 2nd Session (Prof. L. C. MARTIN).
	September	Cambridge (Mass.)	<i>Executive Committee.</i>
		Amsterdam.	<i>Symposium</i> on Spectroscopy at Radiofrequencies (Prof. J. de BOER).
	September	London	<i>Commission</i> on Publications.
	December	✓ Bombay	<i>Symposium</i> on Elementary Particles (Prof. H. J. BHABHA). <i>Commission</i> on Cosmic Rays.

(See p. 4.)

1. The names of some of the organizers are indicated in brackets.

1951	May	✓ Paris	Symposium on Phase contrast and contrast by Interference (Prof. M. FRANÇON).
	June	✓ Brussels	Symposium on Ultrasonics (Prof. HAESAERT and VAN ITTERBEEK).
	July	✓ Copenhagen	Symposium on Quantum Physics (Prof. N. BOHR).
	August	✓ Oxford	7th General Assembly — S. U. N. Commission. Symposium (and Commission) on Very Low Temperatures (Prof. C. J. GORTER and F. E. SIMON).

Plans for the next symposia are given on page 25.

4. The union has for its part responded to Unesco's request that it should take part in enquiries or meetings regarding book coupons and scientific instrument coupons, the preparation and dissemination of abstracts, high altitude research, the fertilization of arid zones, and plans for international laboratories.

5. With Unesco's assistance, the Union of Pure and Applied Physics publishes pamphlets and information bulletins, and documents about the work of its Commissions; it also helps with the publication of papers submitted by those attending meetings, and of the summary of their discussions (see page 29).

6. Fellowships for travel on mission have been allocated by the Executive Committee in accordance with regulations approved by the previous General Assembly. Under a recent Unesco ruling the fellowships will not in future be provided for in the subventions allotted to the Unions. It is hoped nevertheless that some new form of procedure will enable us to continue to facilitate work in laboratories abroad by physicists qualified to derive benefit therefrom (see page 24).

III. — NATIONAL COMMITTEES

Member States numbered twenty-six on 1 november 1951 and several other countries are expected to join. It is, as it always has been desired that physicists all over the world shall take as active as possible a part in the work and administration of the Union.

Various General Assemblies have underlined the prime part that well-organized and active National Committees should play in the Union's work (see page 26).

Below will be found a list (based on information in possession of the Union's Secretary) of the Chairmen and/ or Secretaries and members of the Committees, with the appropriate address for correspondence.

In the case of some countries which have not yet established a Physics Committee the name of the organization fulfilling the function of such a Committee is given.

Argentina : Association Fisica Argentina, Laprida 922, Cordoba.

Australia : (N. C.). Dr. N. A. ESSERMAN, Secretary (C. S. I. R. O., National Standard Laboratory, University Grounds, Chippendale), R. C. L. BOSWORTH, H. G. BRIGGS, C. E. EDDY, Sir Kerr GRANT, A. F. T. HARPER, A. R. HOGG, Sir John MADSEN, L. H. MARTYN, A. D. ROSS, E. L. SAYCE, H. C. WEBSTER, F. G. WHITE.

Belgium : (N. C.). A. de HEMPTINNE, Chairman; A. BIOT, Secretary, 40 rue Liévin de Winne, Ghent; Messrs. COUNSON (Liège) de DONDER (Brussels); HENRIOT (Brussels); JANNE (Liège); de MUYNCK (Louvain); PICCARD (Brussels); de SMEDT (Louvain); Professor UME (École Militaire); Messrs. VERSCHAFFELT (Ghent) and YERNAUX (Mons).

Brazil : Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Fisicas, 21 rue Alvaro Alvim 21 ana, Rio de Janeiro.

Canada : National Research Council, Ottawa.

China : National Academy, Peiping.

Czechoslovakia : Z. HORAK, Vice-Chairman (Karlova nam. 13, Prague II); J. POTOCEK, Secretary (Brno).

Denmark : (N. C.). Det Kongelige Danske Videnskabernes Selskab, Dantesplads, Copenhagen; N. BOHR, Chairman; J. C. JACOBSEN, Secretary; F. H. B. INGERSLEV; H. M. HANSEN; C. MOLLER; E. RASMUSSEN.

Egypt : ALI MUSTAPHA MOSHARRAFA PASHA, MOHAMED FAHMY, MUSTAPHA NAZIF BEY, MOHAMED MAHMOUD GHALY, ADNAN WHALY, MAHMOUD MOUKTAR, AZIZ MILAD FREIDA, ABBAS ALY NASHR, MAHMOUD AHMAD EL CHERIBINY, MOUSTAPHA KAMEL (University Fouad 1st, Cairo).

Finland : HJ V. BROTHERUS, Chairman (Helsinki); L. SIMONS, Secretary (Fisikaliska Inst. Helsingfors Universitet); N. FONTELL; E. LAURILA.

France : The national Committee is including 18 members of the Academy of Science, 18 delegates from the « Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique », 18 delegates from scientific and technical Societies.

President : M. de BROGLIE;

Vice-Presidents : P. FLEURY, L. NEEL, A. PERARD;

Secretaries : P. JACQUINOT, A. MARÉCHAL, 3, boulevard Pasteur, Paris xv^e.

Hungary : Magyar Tudományos Akademia, Budapest.

India : Secretary to the Government of India, Dept. of Scientific Research, New Delhi.

Israel : Research Council of Israel, P. O. B. 607, Jerusalem, Israel.

Italy : (N. C.). E. AMALDI, Secretary (Centro di studio per la fisica nucleare, Città Universitaria, Rome); A. CARRELLI (Naples); E. MEDI (Rome); E. PERUCCA (Turin); G. POLVANI (Milan); F. SCANDONE (Florence).

Japan : Masao KOTANI, Chairman (Tokyo); Minoru KOBAYASHI, Secretary (University of Kyoto); Yoshio FUJIOKA (Tokyo); Seishi KAYA (Tokyo); Seishi KIKUCHI (Osaka); Masazo KIUCHI (Tokyo); Toshinosuke MUTO (Tokyo); Syoiti SAKATA (Nagoya); Koji SATO (Tokyo); Yasumasa TANI (Tokyo); Sin'itiro TOMONAGA (Tokyo); Takahiko YAMANOUCHI (Tokyo).

Mexico : (N. C.). M. SANDOVAL VALLARTA, Secretary (Puente de Alvarado 71, Mexico D. P.); C. GRAEF, A. R. JUARES, J. de OYARZABAL, J. M. RAMIREZ CARAZA, M. L. PERUSQUIA, A. BARAJAS, S. MOSQUEIRA, N. CARRILLO, R. MONGES LOPEZ.

Netherlands : (N. C.). C. J. BAKKER, Chairman (Amsterdam); R. KRONIG, Vice-Chairman (Delft); J. VAN DEN HANDEL, Secretary (Kamerlingh Onnes Laboratorium, Leyden); W. J. BEEKMAN, Treasurer (Utrecht); H. BRINKMAN (Groningen); R. L. KRANS (Arnhem); J. J. de LANCE (Amsterdam); G. W. A. RATHENAU (Eindhoven); F. ZERNIKE (Groningen).

Norway : (N. C.). J. HOLTSMARK, Chairman (Oslo); E. HYLLERAAS, Secretary

(Fysiske Institutt C, Teoretisk Fysikk, Blindern p., Oslo); B. TRUMPY (Bergen); H. WERGELAND (Trondheim).

Poland : C. BIALOBRZESKI, Chairman (Warsaw, Physics Institute, Hoza 69); W. RUBINOWICZ, Vice-Chairman (Warsaw); J. WEYSSENHOFF, Secretary (15, Slowackiego Street, Cracow); M. JEZEWSKI (Cracow); W. RAPUSCINSKI (Warsaw); S. LORIA (Wroclaw); W. MAJEWSKI (Warsaw); H. NIEWODNICZANSKI (Cracow); S. PIENKOWSKI (Warsaw); C. ROLINSKI (Warsaw); A. SOTAN (Warsaw and Lodz); S. SZCZENIOWSKI (Poznan).

Spain : (N. C.). Real Academia de Ciencias Exactas Físicas y Naturales, Valverde 22, Madrid : J. PALACIOS MARTINEZ, E. de RAFAEL, J. M. OTERO Y NAVASQUES, J. A. de ARTIGAS, J. BALTA Y ELIAS, M. CATALAN SANUDO, S. VELAYOS HERMIDA, L. BRU LILASECA, J. CABRERA Y FELIPE, A. COLINO, L. VILLENA PARDO.

Sweden : (N. C.). G. BORELIUS, Chairman; T. GUSTAFSON, T. MAGNUSSON, Vice-Chairmen; E. RUDBERG, Secretary (Metallografiska Institutet, Drottning Kristinasväg 48, Stockholm).

Switzerland : M. A. PERRIER, Chairman (« Le Crêt », chemin du Levant, Lausanne).

Union of South Africa : South African Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, Private Bag 189, Pretoria.

United Kingdom : (N. C.), c/o The Royal Society, Burlington House, Piccadilly, London, W. 1.; N. G. MOTT, Chairman (H. H. Wills Physical Lab., Royal Fort, Bristol).

United States of America : (N. C.). Dr. K. K. DARROW, Chairman (Bell Telephone Laboratories, 463 West Street, New York); S. S. BALLARD (Medford, Mass.); H. A. BARTON (New York); F. C. BRICKWEDDE (Washington); R. B. BRODE (Berkeley); E. HUTCHISSON (Cleveland, Ohio); J. E. MAYER (Chicago); W. SHOCKLEY (New York); J. C. SLATER (Cambridge, Mass.); M. A. TUVE, A. T. WATERMAN, J. A. WHEELER (Princeton).

IV. — SPECIAL COMMISSIONS

(See Article 6 of the statutes, page 28.)

We describe hereunder the present state of these Commissions' work as well as their composition as decided upon by the 7th General Assembly. The dates of present member's nominations are given in brackets.

S. 1. — Finance Commission.

Members : E. BAUER (Paris); C. J. GORTER (Leiden) (1947).

The Union's accounts for the period 1948-1950, budget estimates for the following years, and the report of the Finance Commission are the subject of publication S. G. 51-6 and were approved by the last General Assembly (see below page 16).

S. 2. — S. U. N. Commission (Symbols, Units and Nomenclature).

(1947) A. PERARD (Paris), Chairman until 1 January 1952;
(1948) H. KONIG (Bern), Chairman from 1 January 1952;
(1948) J. de BOER, Secretary, 98 Bunsenstraat, Amsterdam;
(1948) E. PERUCCA (Turin);

(1951) J. CABANNES (Paris); E. GUGGENHEIM (Reading); J. H. VAN VLECK (Cambridge, Mass.).

Established in 1931 and reconstituted in 1947, this Commission met in London (July 1947), in Amsterdam (July 1948) and in Copenhagen (July 1951).

Documents published : S. U. N. 48-1 to 5 (see I. U. P. 2, page 23); S. U. N. 49-1; S. U. N. 51-1 to 4 (see below, page 29).

After adoption by the General Assembly in 1948 this Commission's proposals were considered by the 9th General Conference on Weights and Measures (1948). The proposals (see I. U. P. 2, pages 5 and 6) concerned the use of the joule as the unit of heat; the definition of the thermodynamic scale of temperature based on the triple point of water as the single fixed point; the use recommended for international purposes of a practical system based on the meter, the kilogram (mass), the second, and an electrical unit of the absolute practical system (without the abandonment by physicists of the C. G. S. system, being recommended); the selection of the term « Newton » to indicate the unit of force in this system; and the publication of first report « General Rules, Symbols for Physical Quantities Symbols for Units » (doc. S. U. N. 49-1).

In 1951, an important report (doc. S. U. N. 51-1) prepared by Prof. de BOER enabled the Commission, after three meetings, to agree upon suggestions which were submitted to the General Assembly. After a few amendments, they were adopted in the following form :

1. It is recommended to avoid the use of the word « billion » in the scientific literature. It is recommended to use e. q either 10^9 eV or GeV (« giga electron volt ») as accepted by the I. U. P. A. P. en 1948.

2. *Numerals attached to symbols for chemical elements.* After a thorough discussion the S. U. N. Committee has decided, in spite of possible objections relating to the cost of type setting, not to modify the recommendations made in 1948.

3. The I. U. P. A. P. recommends to physicists who wish to reserve the name « isotopes » for different atoms of the same atomic number, the use of the word nuclide to indicate a species of atoms identical as regards atomic number, mass number.

This recommendation is contingent on the approval of the I. U. C. A. P.¹

4. The practical system of units, to be called Giorgi-system or M. K. S. A.-system, should be based on the four units; the meter, the kilogram (mass), the second and the ampere; for certain purposes an equivalent alternative choice of four independent units may be made.

5. Considering that in the near future the C. G. S. systems and the M. K. S. A.-system will be simultaneously in use in pure and applied physics, — to facilitate the conversion of the units of the C. G. S. systems into the M. K. S. A.-system and vice versa:

It is recommended to introduce for the purpose of developing the definition of secondary units the following C. G. S. system based on four principal units :

a) The electrostatic C. G. S. — system or C. G. S. e. system, based on the centimeter, gram (mass), second and the electrostatic unit of electric charge.

b) The electromagnetic C. G. S. system or C. G. S. m. system based on the centimeter, gram (mass), second and the decaampere.

¹ This approval was given by the General Assembly of the Union of Chemistry (Washington, September 1951).

6. *Rationalisation of electromagnetic equations.* a) It is recommended that the I. U. P. A. P. should propose to the International Electrotechnical Committee the formation of a Joint-Commission to discuss and make the recommendations on all questions connected with the rationalisation of electromagnetic quantities.

b) It is not desirable to recommend for physicists the exclusive use either of rationalised or of non rationalised equations.

c) If the equations are rationalised the S. U. N. Committee considers that the rationalisation should be effected by the introduction of new quantities.

7. The International Union of Physics authorizes publication of the list of symbols recommended and adopted by the S. U. N. Commission in 1951.

✓ S. 3. — Commission on Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics.

(1948) J. MAYER (Chicago), Chairman;

(1947) I. PRIGOGINE, Secretary (50 Avenue F. D. Roosevelt, Brussels);

(1947) E. BAUER (Paris);

(1948) J. A. BEATTIE (Cambridge, Mass.);

(1951) S. R. de GROOT (Utrecht); G. S. RUSHBROOKE (New-Castle, U. K.).

Established in 1947 as the « Commission on Thermodynamics Quantities and Symbols », this Commission met in July 1947 in London and January 1948 in Brussels. Its terms of reference having been widened by the General Assembly of 1948, it took part in organizing a Symposium on the Present Problems of Statistical Mechanics, which was held in Florence in 1949.

It is intended to hold in 1952, in Paris a symposium on the Thermodynamics of Phase transitions (see page 25).

✓ S. 4. — Commission on Cosmic Rays.

(1947) P. M. S. BLACKETT (Manchester), Chairman;

(1951) L. LEPRINCE-RINGUET, Secretary (17, rue Descartes, Paris ve);

(1948) C. D. ANDERSON (Pasadena, Calif.); G. BERNARDINI (Rome); H. J. BHABHA (Bombay); M. S. VALLARTA (Mexico).

This Commission was established in 1947 and met in Cracow in October of that year; at its suggestion, the General Assembly recommended in 1948, the use of the terms : positon, negaton, nucleon and meson (see I. U. P. 2, p. 6).

This commission helped to organize the symposia at Como (1949) and Bombay (1950); the next is to be held in 1953.

A directory of laboratories and physicists taking part in research on cosmic rays has been published (R. C. 49-1) and will be brought up to date periodically.

During the Bombay Congress, the following physicists : E. AMALDI, H. J. BHABHA, P. M. S. BLACKETT, L. LEPRINCE-RINGUET, C. MAILGAVANAM, C. MOLLER and PETERS gave favourable consideration to plans for the creation or development of research laboratories in high altitudes, especially in the Himalayas. No request for special credits for this purpose was foreseen, but it was thought that U. N. E. S. C. O.'s intervention with the governments concerned would be most valuable.

Attention was drawn to the value of research on cosmic rays at different latitudes and it was recommended that subsidies should be granted which would allow staff to be transferred for such research to existing laboratories.

S. 5. — Commission on Very Low temperatures.

- (1949) F. E. SIMON (Oxford), President;
(1949) C. J. GORTER, Secretary, Nieuwsteeg 18 (Leyden);
(1951) K. CLUSIUS (Zurich); C. E. LANE (Newhaven, Conn.).

Document T. B. T. 51-1 gives an account of the activities of this commission, which began work in Cambridge (Mass.) in 1949, after a preparatory meeting, in 1948 (see doc. S. G. 48-7); another meeting with limited attendance was held at Oxford in August 1951.

The Commission cooperates with the First Commission of the International Institute on Refrigeration, the President and Secretary of which are at present Co-Presidents of the Commission.

It has endeavoured to reestablish cooperation between American refrigerating experts and the Institute.

The Commission stressed the importance of establishing a scale of uniform temperatures in the domain of liquid helium by the magnetic method and also by that of gas thermometry. It asked for the setting up of a translating centre for scientific memoranda published in Russian and deplored the increasing tendency to publish scientific results only in the form of short notes, letters to the editor and even reports intended only for limited distribution.

These remarks were taken into consideration by the General Assembly in 1951 (see p. 22).

S. 6. — Publications Commission.

- (1949) J. H. AWBERY (London), President;
(1949) G. A. BOUTRY, Secretary, 23, rue du Re trail, Paris;
(1949) M. FIERZ (Basel); A. D. FOKKER (Amsterdam); E. HUTCHINSON (Cleveland);
E. PERUCCA (Turin).

In 1948, the General Assembly of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics adopted (see I. U. P. A. P. 2., p. 7) various decisions and recommendations concerning: the summaries (in french and english) that should accompany any publication of original work appearing in a review on physics; the coordination of « progress reports », and a history of the development of physics.

The Publications Commission, constituted in 1949, has carried on its work by correspondence and met in London in September 1950 (see Doc. S. G. 50-1 and Publ. 51-1). Certain members were also able to meet at meetings of Unesco's committees of experts and also at those of the Joint Commission of the International Council of Unions for Physics Abstracts.

The Publications Commission of the International Union of Pure and applied Physics devoted most its time to studying the problem of cooperating with this Joint Commission (see p. 14). It also examined schemes for the publication of specialized international reviews (Acustica and Optica Acta) and approved these schemes they would have the effect of limiting the number of national specialized reviews and that they raised no objection on the part of the American Societies for Acoustics and Optics and on the further condition that the new reviews publish no lists of titles, resumé or abstracts.

The General Assembly submitted to the Publications Commission a suggestion from the Commission on Very Low Temperatures aimed at avoiding the abuse of « letters to the editor » (see p. 9). It also adopted the following recommendation, coming

from the same source : « In view of the importance of Russian contributions to Physics and related Sciences, the I. U. P. A. P. would welcome an information and translation service available to interested. The I. U. P. A. P. accordingly requests its Committee on Publications and asks the Executive Committee of I. C. S. U. to consider the possibility of issuing a Journal of translations established with the cooperation of existing partial documentary services.

S. 7. — Acoustics Commission.

- (1951) R. D. BOLT (Cambridge, Mass.), President;
- (1951) C. W. KOSTEN, Secretary (Mijnbouwplein 11, Delft);
- (1951) F. CANAC (Marseille); A. GIACOMINI (Rome); F. INGERSLEV (Copenhagen);
- (1951) E. MEYER (Göttingen); W. P. WILSON (Tadworth, U. K.).

This Commission was constituted by the last General Assembly (see p. 22).

S. 8. — Solid State Commission.

Being constituted on a request from I. C. S. U.

This Commission was constituted by the Executive Committee provisionally as follows :

Union of Physics : MM. G. P. THOMSON (Londres), R. SMOLUCHOWSKI (Pittsburgh, Penn.), E. J. VERWEY (Eindhoven), J. C. SLATER (Cambridge, Mass.)

Union of Crystallography : MM. P. P. EWALD, Secretary (Polytechnic Institute of Brooklyn, 99 Livingstone Street, Brooklyn 2 New-York, N. Y.); COULSON (Oxford), A. GUINIER (Paris).

V. — JOINT COMMISSIONS

and representatives of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics
on the commissions belonging to other Unions

(See article 6 of the Statutes, page 28 of the french text.)

The Joint Commissions are constituted by decision of the International Council of Scientific Unions, which organizes their meetings. They comprise members of several unions that are interested in their activities; one of them, known as the Parent-Union, exercises when necessary the right of oversight over the Commission's scientific activities.

On the other hand, certain Unions may be invited or authorized to be represented on organs belonging to another Union; a case of this is recorded above (D. 1).

✓ **Commission on Rheology (Viscosity).**

Two delegates from the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics : (1947) J. M. BURGERS, Secretary, 1 van Houtenstraat, Delft; G. W. SCOTT BLAIR (Reading, U. K.).

Two delegates from the International Union of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics (Parent-Union) : K. O. PEDERSON (Upsala); C. SADRON (Strasbourg);

Four delegates from the International Union of Biological Sciences : P. EGGLETON (Edinburgh); H. EYRING (Salt Lake City, Utah); A. FREY-WYSSLING (Zurich); G. VAN ITERSON (Baarn, Netherlands).

Two delegates from the International Union of Chemistry : Mrs. A. DOBRY-DUCLAUX (Paris); R. SIGNER (Bern).

Two delegates from the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics : Th. Von KARMAN, President (Pasadena, Calif.); Sir G. I. TAYLOR (Cambridge, U. K.).

The Commission met in London (September 1947), at Scheveningen (September 1948) and at Lund (Sweden) in July 1950 at the same time as a symposium was held on rheological problem in biology. The dissolution of this commission is foreseen, after the eventually creation of an International Association of Rheological Societies which would adhere to the Union of Mechanics.

Documents published : « Reports on the principles of rheological nomenclature » in the Proceedings of the International Congress on Rheology, Holland, 1948.

✓ Commission on Radio-activity (Units, Constants, Standards, Nomenclature).

Six delegates from the International Union of Physics : Sir J. COCKROFT (Harwell, U. K.); L. F. CURTISS (Washington, D. C.); R. D. EVANS (Cambridge, Mass.); J. C. JACOBSEN (Copenhagen); Mrs. JOLIO-CURIE (Paris); G. J. SZOO, Secretary (Lairesstraat 174, Amsterdam).

And six from the International Union of Chemistry (Parent-Union) : Miss E. GLEDITSCH (Oslo); G. HEVESY (Stockholm); W. C. JOHNSON (Chicago); F. JOLIO (Paris); F. A. PANETH (Durham, U. K.) President; G. T. SEABORG (Berkeley, Calif.).

Consultative Committee : Sir James CHADWICK (Cambridge, U. K.); O. HAHN (Göttingen); B. KARLICK (Vienna); Sc. LIND (Minneapolis); J. C. PICCARD (Brussels).

Constituted in 1948 to follow up the Radioactive Units Commission of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics (formed in 1947), partial meeting in London in July 1947 (see doc. S. G. 47-3). The joint commission also succeeds the « Atomic » and « Radioactive Constants » Commissions of the International Union of Chemistry as well as the former « Radium Standard Committee ». The Commission met at Amsterdam in September 1949, then in Paris in July 1950 and in New-York in September 1951 on the occasion of the 16th Conference of the International Union of Chemistry.

We extract the following information from the report of July 1951 by the Secretary of the Joint Commission.

Radium standards:

The ownership of the International Radium Standard, prepared by HÖNIGSCHMIDT in 1934, consisting of 22.23 mg pure RaCl_2 , has been transferred from the former International Radium Standard Commission to the Joint Commission. The surviving members of the Int. Radium Standard Commission have given their consent for this transfer.

The Standard will remain under the care of the Bureau International des Poids et des Mesures. It will be allowed to transport the Standard for the sake of measurements to the Laboratoire CURIE at Paris. In this case M^{me} JOLIO-CURIE will have the responsibility for the Standard. For other use of the Standard the consent of the Commission will be required. Negotiations are going on with the Curatorium of the Institut für Radium-forschung at Vienna to transfer the ownership of the second International Radium Standard, consisting of 31.17 mg pure RaCl_2 , which was also prepared by HÖNIGSCHMIDT and which is the property of the Vienna Academy of Science, and is under the care of the Radium Institute, also to the Joint Commission.

The Joint Commission decided that a comparison will be made of the available secondary radium standards by the Laboratoire CURIE.

The Joint Commission decided to promote the exchange of gamma-ray standards of artificial radioactive isotopes as well as of beta-ray standards among various laboratories, for the sake of comparison of the methods of measurement.

The Commission recommended that the *curies* shall be maintained as the only unit of radioactivity but that the old definition of the curie shall be replaced by the following definition :

« The curie is the unit of radioactivity defined as the quantity of any radioactive nuclide in which the number of disintegrations per second is 3.700×10^{10} . »

The Commission recommended the following abbreviations : c for curie; mc for millicurie; μ c for microcurie; kc for kilocurie.

The Commission stated that the word « barn » for 10^{-24} cm² as unit of cross-section for nuclear processes is now in common usage and should be accepted.

Publications : an article on « Radioactive Standards and Units » containing a report of the work of the Joint Commission, has been written by the president and published in *Nature* of December 2nd, 1950.

The minutes of the meeting of the Joint Commission in Paris, 1950, has been published in the Report of the Executive Committee 1950 of the International Council of Scientific Unions.

✓ **Commission on Physico-Chemical Data.**

Two delegates from the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics : (1948) G. BORELIUS (Stockholm); (1951) H. KÖNIG (Berne).

Four delegates from the International Union of Chemistry (Parent-Union) : E. MOLES (Madrid); W. SWIETOSLAWSKI (Warsaw); E. R. SMITH, Secretary (U. S. A.); J. P. WIBAUT, Président (Amsterdam).

This committee met in London in July 1947 (see doc. S. G. 47-3, page 4, and Records of the 14th Conference of the International Union of Chemistry, page 71), in Amsterdam in September 1949 (see Records of the Fifteenth Conference of the International Union of Chemistry, page 55) and in New-York in September 1951.

It has care of the International Office of Physico-Chemical Standards with a consultative committee constituted as follows : E. BARTOW (Iowa City, U. S. A.), M. BECKERS (Brussels); M. DELEPINE (Paris); Sir Alfred EGERTON (London); F. GIORDANI (Naples); D. A. MACINNES (New-York); P. JOLIBOIS (Paris); N. KEESOM (Leyden); S. C. LIND (Minneapolis); G. NATTA (Milan); J. SMITTENBERG (Utrecht); S. SUGDEN (London); E. WICHERS (Washington).

✓ **Commission on the Ionosphere.**

Two delegates from the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics : (1947) H. S. W. MASSEY (London); L. VEGARD (Oslo).

Four delegates from the International Radio Scientific Union (Parent-Union) : Sir E. D. APPLETON, President (London); W. J. G. BEYNON, Secretary (University College, Swansea U. K.); F. D. MARTYN (Canberra, Australia); N. SMITH (Washington).

Four delegates from the International Union of Astronomy : M. FESENKOF (Moscow); B. LYOT (Paris); D. H. MENZEL (Cambridge, Mass.); R. V. D. WOOLEY (Canberra).

Four delegates from the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics : L. BERKNER (Washington); S. CHAPMAN (Oxford, U. K.); A. H. R. GOLDIE (Harrow, U. K.); Leiv HARRANG (Tromsø, Norway).

This Commission held a limited meeting at Lyon in September 1947 (see doc. S. G. 47-4, p. 4), met in Brussels in July 1948 (see doc. 48-8, p. 6) and in September 1950 (see doc. S. G. 51-5, pp. 5 and 6). Next meeting at Sydney (Australia) in 1952.

✓ **Commission on Radiometry.**

A representative of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics : (1947) E. G. BOWEN (Sydney).

Four delegates from the Radio-Scientific Union (Parent-Union) : H. G. BOOKER (Cambridge, U. K.); R. C. BURROWS, President (Ithaca); R. P. LEJAY (Paris); I. LUZEON (Zurich).

Three delegates from the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics : A. PERLAT (Paris); P. A. SHEPPARD (London); H. WEXLER (Washington).

Two co-opted members : W. E. GORDON, Secretary (Cornell Univ. Ithaca) and O. RYDBERG (Göteborg).

This Commission held a preparatory meeting at Toronto in August 1947 (see page 9 of the Bulletin of the International Radio-Scientific Union for February 1948) and a meeting at Stockholm in July 1948 (see doc. S. G. 48-11, p. 4). It met in Brussels in August 1951 (see doc. S. G. 52-1, p. 5).

✓ Commission on High Altitude Research Stations.

Three delegates from the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics : (1949) R. D. BRODE (Berkeley); J. CLAY (Amsterdam); M. PERUTZ (Cambridge, U. K.).

Four delegates from the International Union of Biological Sciences (Parent-Union) : L. EMBERGER (France); C. MONGE, Président (Peru); C. SALT (U. K.); R. STAMFELI, Secretary (5 Buhlplatz, Berne).

Three delegates from the International Union of Astronomy : D. H. MENZEL, President (U. S. A.); J. RÖSH (France); M. WALDMEIER (Switzerland).

Four delegates from the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics : M. D. QUERVAIN (Switzerland); F. W. CÖTZ (Switzerland); K. R. RAMANATHAN (India); J. A. BROGGI (Peru).

This commission held its first meeting in Bagnères-de-Bigorre (France) in August 1950 (see doc. S. G. 50-3, p. 5). Next meeting intended at Colorado (U. S. A.) in 1952.

✓ Commission on Spectroscopy.

Three delegates from the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics : J. C. BAKKER, Secretary (Zeeman Laboratorium, Muidergrachtpl. 4, Amsterdam); G. HARRISON (U. S. A.); P. JACQUINOT (France); R. A. JENKINS (U. S. A.); R. D. PEARSE (U. K.); S. PIENKOWSKI (Poland).

Six delegates from the International Union of Astronomy : B. EDLEN (Sweden); A. GATTERER (Vatican City); G. HERZBERG (U. S. A.); W. F. MEGGERS (U. S. A.), Président; Mrs C. E. MORE-SITTERLEY (U. S. A.); P. SWINGS (Belgium).

Honorary President : Prof. J. N. RUSSEL.

Advisers : J. E. MACK (U. S. A.) and R. S. MULLIKEN (U. S. A.).

This commission, the constitution of which was decided by the Council of Scientific Unions in September 1948, met first in September 1950 at Cambridge (U. K.) (see doc. S. G. 50-3, p. 7). It is to meet again at Rome, in September 1952.

✓ Commission on Radiobiology.

Two members of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics : P. MAYNEORD (London); R. D. EVANS (Cambridge, U. S. A.).

Six delegates of the International Union of Biological Sciences : P. BONNET-MAURY, Secretary (Institut du Radium, 11, rue Pierre-Curie, Paris 5^e); L. H. GRAY (U. K.); F. J. SPEAR (U. K.); G. HEVESY (Sweden), Président; A. LACASSAGNE (France); J. H. LAWRENCE (U. S. A.); C. CHAGAS (Brazil).

Two delegates from the International Union of Chemistry : MELANDER (Sweden); M^{me} JOLIO-CURIE (France).

This Commission held its first session in Paris in July 1950 : it was decided to create a sub-commission entrusted with submitting a proposal for an international institute and with collecting existing documentation on the definition and measurement of radio-sensibility. The commission is to meet again at Stockholm in August 1952.

Commission on Abstracts in Pure and Applied Physics.

Four delegates from the International Union of Physics (Parent-Union) : G. A. BOUTRY (292, rue Saint-Martin, Paris), Secretary; J. A. AWBERY (U. K.); K. K. DARROE (U. S. A.); E. PERUCCA (Turin).

A delegate from the International Union of Astronomy : P. BOURGEOIS, President (Belgium).

A delegate from the International Union of Crystallography : A. J. C. WILSON (U.K.).

A delegate from the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics : J. LACLAVERE (France).

A delegate from the International Union of the History of Sciences : J. PELSENER (Belgium).

A delegate from the International Union of Theoretical applied Mechanics : J. PERES (France).

A delegate from the International Radio-Scientific Union : E. HERBAYS (Belgium).

This Commission met in Paris in July 1951 and formulated the following resolutions, which were approved by the last General Assembly of the International Union of Physics :

1. The Commission takes note of the collaboration already established between *Science Abstracts* and *Bulletin analytique* and expresses its satisfaction and gratitude to the editors of these two periodicals.

2. It has been agreed that, so far as French non-periodical publications are concerned, the editor of *Bulletin analytique* will do his best to send all necessary information to *Science Abstracts*, while the editor of *Science Abstracts* will do the same in regard to similar publications appearing in the United Kingdom.

4. The Joint Commission for Abstracts on Pure and Applied Physics has noted that the Bureau of I. C. S. U. has agreed to the creation of an International Abstracts Service to be considered as a permanent scientific activity of the Council. After a thorough discussion of the implications of such a decision, the Commission unanimously decided to ask the Bureau of I. C. S. U. to dissolve the present Joint Commission and to set up a Bureau for an International Abstracts Service. The constitution of this Bureau will be limited and the following will be represented in it :

a) The council of I. C. S. U.

b) Abstracts review, admitted as members (beginning with *Science Abstracts* and *Bulletin analytique*).

A secretary would be appointed by I. C. S. U.

The commission hopes that measures will be taken to keep the unions regularly informed on the service's activities.

3. The Commission recommends that the editors of periodicals be asked, through the constituent unions to make the titles of articles as explicit as possible.

5. The Commission recommends to I. C. S. U. that a minimum subsidy of \$ 2.000 be granted to the Bureau for 1952.

6. The Commission asks its Secretary to request the constituent Unions of the Joint Commission to make urgent representations, through their national Committees, to publishers of periodicals in order to obtain rapid transmission of reviews to the General Abstracts Service on the most favourable terms.

The precedent proposals have been approved by the Executive Committee of I. C. S. U.

Commission on Solide State (creation postponed).

In pursuance of a request from the International Union of Crystallography it was proposed to the International Council of Scientific Unions that a new Joint Commission on Solid States should be set up. If this Commission materialize the representatives of the Union will be : Sir G. P. THOMSON, Chairman (London); R. SMOLUCHOWSKI (Pittsburgh); E. J. W. VERWEY (Eindhoven).

The Executive Committee delayed (in October 1951) the creation of these Joint-Commission and proposed a specialised Commission of I. U. P. A. P. be first created, in which would take part delegates of I. U. Cr.

Commission on electronic Microscopy (being constituted).

Creation decided by the Executive Committee of I. C. S. U. (October 1951).

Will take part the Unions of Physics (Parent-Union), of Biology, Chemistry and Crystallography:

✓ Macromolecular Chemistry (Commission of the International Union of Chemistry).

Chairman : H. MARKS (U. S. A.); Secretary : G. CHAMPETIER (France).

Representatives of the I. U. P. A. P. : J. D. BERNAL (London); P. DEBYE (Ithaca, N. J.).

Three sub-commissions : standards, nomenclature and publications.

This commission met last at Washington (1951) (see minutes of the General Assembly of I. U. C. A. C.). A Symposium on « Radiations and macromolecules » is proposed at Stockholm in May 1952.

VI. — INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION OF OPTICS

Our Union has till now only one « Affiliated Commission », according to article 6 of the statutes (amended in 1948) : The Commission on Optics (I. C. O.).

It held in July 1948, after the General Assembly of the Union, a constitutive meeting at Delft (see doc. C. I. O. 2) and in July 1950 another plenary session at London, jointly to an important optical Instruments Conference, organized by the British Optical Committee.

National Optical Committees adhering to the Commission : Belgium, Czechoslovakia, U. S. A., France, Great-Britain, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland.

Its Bureau is constituted at present, as follows :

Chairman : Dr. A. C. S. Van HEEL;
 Vice-Chairmen : MM. S. S. BALLARD, L. D. MARTIN, J. M. OTERO NAVASCUES;
 Secretary General : P. FLEURY;
 Tresorier : A. ARNULF.

Are to be found in the publication *Optica Acta* (may 1951), sent to all the National Committees of Physics, the minutes (in english and french) of the meeting at London and the text of the decisions, relating particularly at classification in optics and at unification attempt of conventions and Symbols (limited at essentials) — recommendations concerning various experiences in physiological optics in view of applications to instrumental optics, concerning also the choice of temperatures and standard wave-lengths...

VII. — FINANCIAL POSITION

1. Accounts for 1948, 1949 and 1950

(Approved by the General Assembly, see page 00.)

(For previous years, see doc. S. G. 48-3, April 1948.)

Since 1947, it would be mentioned that the Union's income has consisted of two separated parts : subscriptions by member countries (Account A); and grants made by Unesco for specific purposes (Account B).

ACCOUNT A (UNION)

	Dollar		
<i>Receipts :</i>			
Subscriptions received in 1948			1 029.37
Subscriptions received in 1949			2 500
Subscriptions received in 1950			8 920
Revenue from Investment			8.97
			7 458.34
			47.7
Less : Losses on exchange			7 410.5
 <i>Expenditure :</i>			
	1948	1949	1950
a) Publications, translations, secretariat	241.95	251.28	356.8
b) Office and postal expenses	243	254.71	209.8
c) Accountancy and banking costs	16.52	35.16	61.6
d) Travel, congresses, unforeseen expenses	313.92	273.02	364.4
e) Subscription to I. C. S. U.	—	—	25.1
	815.39	814.17	1 018.7
Totaux			2 648.26

Summary :

Assets as at 1 January 1948.	937.15
Receipts 1948, 1949 and 1950.	7 410.51
Total.	<u>8 347.66</u>
Expenditure	2 648.26
Assets as at 31 December 1950	<u>5 699.40</u>

N. B. — Part of the subscriptions received in 1949 and 1950 were paid on behalf of the *International Commission on Optics*, which is affiliated to the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics. These subscriptions amounted to 1 820 dollars.

After a detailed examination of expenditure, Mr. ARNULF, Treasurer of I. C. O. and the members of the Finance Committee of the Union agreed that I. C. O. should pay one quarter of the Union's expenditure for 1948-1950 (that is \$ 662, to the nearest dollars.

I. C. O.'s assets as at 1 January 1951 are therefore estimated at :
\$ 1 820 — \$ 662 = \$ 1 158

ACCOUNT B (U. N. E. S. C. O.)

Receipts :

Sums received from Unesco in 1948	17 300
Sums received from Unesco in 1949	18 492.20
Sums received from Unesco in 1950	19 480
Total.	<u>55 272.20</u>

Expenditure :

	Liquidation of the year 1947	1948	1949	1950	
				liquidated	obligated
a) Executive Committee Commissions.	2 587	5 085.90	1 463.92	3 334.20	—
b) Symposia.	1 911	3 924.80	8 267.52	8 334.20	461.40
c) Travel (Chairman and Secretary).	30	287	482.09	49.16	92
d) Fellowships.	1 000	4 000	2 500	900	1 100
e) Publications.	—	2 742	3 500	1 461.98	638.02
Totaux	<u>5 528</u>	<u>16 039.7</u>	<u>16 213.53</u>	<u>14 269.73</u>	<u>2 291.42</u>
			54 342.38		

Summary :

Assets as at 31 December 1947.	5 675.50
Receipts	55 272.30
Total.	<u>60 947.70</u>
Expenditure.	54 342.38
Assets.	<u>6 605.32</u>

The assets are composed as follows :

Authorized Transfers on 1951	4 560
Advances on future grants.	2 045.32
	<hr/>
Total	6 605.32
Outstanding obligations.	2 291.42
	<hr/>
<i>In hand.</i>	8 896.74

2. — BALANCE SHEET AS AT 31 DECEMBER 1950

	<i>Dollars</i>
Account A : Int. Union of Pure and Applied Physics	5 699.40
Account B.	8 896.74
	<hr/>
	14 596.14
Creditors	2 369.37
	<hr/>
	16 965.51

Composition of Assets :

<i>Stocks and Shares (Crédit Algérien)</i>	<i>Amount</i>	<i>Rate of Conversion</i>	<i>Dollars</i>
Dollars.			12 057.97
English pounds	543,13.1	2.54	1 382.52
French francs.	385 792	0.28	1 080.21
Belgian francs.	7 740.80	1.92	139.20
Swiss francs.	3 069.90	23.31	715.59
Dutch florins.	2 014.93	22.38	450.94
Italian lire	631 322	630	1 002.10
Bank : Frs. F.	18 915	0.28	52.98
Holdings :			
15 Government bonds.			
F. F. (at par).	30 000	0.28	84
			<hr/>
Total			16 965.51

*Je soussigné, Maurice Cimetière, Expert-Comptable assermenté, membre de l'Ordre
Commissaire aux comptes près la Cour d'Appel de Paris, certifie avoir vérifié les présents
comptes et les avoir reconnus exacts.*

Signé : M. CIMETIÈRE.

8. — BUDGET ESTIMATES

ACCOUNT A (UNION)

Receipts :

Subscriptions of member countries	1951	1952
	4 000	4 000

Expenditure :

Publications, translations, Secretariat	1 200	800
Office and postal expenses	500	400
Accountancy and banks	60	60
Travel, congresses, unforeseen expenses	1 200	800
Subscription to the International Council of Scientific Unions	40	40
	<hr/>	<hr/>
I. C. O.'s Expenditure	3 000	2 100
	<hr/>	<hr/>
	1 000	1 500
	<hr/>	<hr/>
	4 000	3 600

ACCOUNT B (U. N. E. S. C. O.)

Receipts :

Authorized carrying-forward of grants already received	1951
Grants made for 1951	4 560
	<hr/>
Total	12 850
	<hr/>
	17 410

Expenditure :

a) Executive Committee and Commissions	4 600
b) Symposia	5 860
c) Fellowships	2 000
d) Publications	4 950
	<hr/>
Total	17 410

4. — REPORT OF THE FINANCE COMMISSION

We have examined the accounts and balance-sheet presented above and noted their conformity with the vouchers. We recommend the General Assembly to, approve them as well as the draft budget.

The Union's assets, which had diminished from 1 254 dollars (on 1 January 1947) to 937 dollars (on 1 January 1948), have gradually increased to 5 700 dollars (on 1 January 1951), including 1 158 dollars for the International Commission on Optics.

Although this reserve is small for an International Union, it will henceforth permit the Executive Committee to assume certain obligations, particularly with regard to

expenditure in which U. N. E. S. C. O. has been asked to participate, without awaiting the sometimes delayed decision of that Organization, and even at the risk of the grant being partly or wholly refused.

The number of participating States has grown very considerably and the number of States which are behindhand in the payment of their subscriptions is relatively small; however the amount of the subscriptions already received remains less than the sums received from U. N. E. S. C. O. in the form of grants. As the Secretary-General's report indicates (doc. SG. 51-2, par. d), it is necessary to take into account the larger financial contribution which is made by member states indirectly to the functioning of our Union.

But, in our opinion, the precarious nature of all external aid makes it most desirable that our Union should obtain larger regular resources, either through higher subscription or in some other way.

The following table offers a useful comparison :

<i>Unions :</i>	<i>Maximum subscription</i>
Astronomical Union	\$ 1,280
Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry.	\$ 675
Union of Crystallography	\$ 900
Union of Geodesy and of Geophysics	\$ 2,240
Geographical Union.	\$ 1,500
Union of Pure and Applied Physics.	\$ 320 (+ \$ 160 for I. C. O.)
Scientific Radio Union	\$ 1,160

April 1951

E. BAUER · C. J. GORTER.

VIII. — REPORT ON THE SEVENTH GENERAL ASSEMBLY (1951)

1. The General Assembly was held at Copenhagen, in the Conference Room of the Danish Academy of Sciences, Dantespladz; the President was Professor H. A. KRAMERS.

Meetings were held, in the afternoon, on 11, 12 and 13 July.

The following were present as members of the Executive Committee (E), delegates of National Committees (D), or members of Commission (C).

Argentina : J. A. BALSEIRO (D).

Australia : E. O. HERCUS (D).

Belgium : C. MANNEBACK (D), I. PRIGOGINE (C).

Brazil : B. GROSS (D).

Canada : J. S. FOSTER (D), L. E. HOWLETT (D).

Danmark : N. BOHR (D), J. C. JACOBSEN (E, D), C. MOLLER (D).

Finland : N. FONTELL (D), L. SIMONS (D).

France : E. BAUER (D, C), G. A. BOUTRY (C), J. CABANNES (D), G. DARRIEUS (D)
P. FLEURY (E), A. PÉRARD (D, C), A. PROCA (D).

India : Sir K. S. KRISHNAN (D), J. H. BHABHA (D).

Italy : E. AMALDI (D, E), A. CARRELLI (D), B. FERRETTI (D), E. PERUCCA (D, C)
G. WATAGHIN (D).

Japan : Masao KOTANI (D), Shizuo MIYAKE (D).

Netherlands : C. J. BAKKER (D), J. de BOER (D. C), C. J. GORTER (E), H. A. KRAMERS (E), C. W. KOSTEN (C).

Norway : J. HOLTSMARK (D), E. HYLLERAAS (D).

Sweden : E. HULTHEN (D), I. WALLER (D).

Switzerland : H. KÖNIG (C), H. MERCIER (D), P. SCHERRER (E).

United Kingdom : J. H. AWBERY (D, C), Sir C. DARWIN (E), E. GRIFFITHS (C), E. A. GUGGENHEIM (D, C), H. S. W. MASSEY (D), F. E. SIMON (D), Sir G. P. THOMSON (D).

United States of America : H. A. BARTON (D), K. K. DARROW (E), D. M. DENNISON (D), P. P. EWALD (E), E. HUTCHISSON (D), T. LAURITSEN (D), H. H. NIELSEN (D, C), J. C. SLATER (E), L. A. TURNER (D), J. R. NIELSEN (D), J. A. WHEELER (D).

A number of other members of National Committees were also present at some or all of the meetings, as were the following :

P. AUGER, Director of Unesco's Department of Natural Sciences;

R. FRASER, Observer appointed by the International Council of Scientific Unions;

J. NIELSEN, Observer appointed by the International Union of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics;

B. REINBERG, Observer appointed by the International Union of Biological Sciences;

J. RYDBER, Observer appointed by the International Radio Scientific Union;

S. VEIBEL, Observer appointed by the International Union of Chemistry.

The following countries which belong to the Union were unable to send representatives to the General Assembly : China, Czechoslovakia, Egypt, Hungary, Mexico, Poland, Spain, Union of South Africa.

The Executive Committee held meetings, before and after the meetings of the General Assembly, on 11 July (morning and evening), 12 July (morning) and 13 July (morning and evening). The Commission on Symbols, Units and Nomenclature met on 11, 12 and 13 July (morning).

Before the General Assembly, from 6 to 10 July, a symposium on Problems of Quantum Physics was organized by Professor Niels BOHR and Professor S. ROSENTHAL; this symposium was most successful and will be the subject of a separate report.

The Committee for the organization of this symposium and the « Kongelige Danske Videnskabernes Selskab », in the persons of its Secretary, Professor J. NIELSEN, and Mr. A. LOMHOLT, made excellent arrangements for the reception of those attending the General Assembly (who were entertained to lunch each day by the Danish Academy), for the material organization of the meetings, and for the rapid reproduction of various documents. The warmest gratitude of the Union is due to them.

First meeting, Wednesday, 11 July.

2. The meeting opened at 2 p. m. Professor Niels BOHR, President of the Danish Academy of Science, welcomed the members of the Assembly and expressed his hopes for the success of their work.

Professor H. A. KRAMERS, President of the Union, thanked Professor Bohr and gave a brief sketch of the progress made by the Union since its last General Assembly (1948) with regard to both the number of participating countries (17 being represented

at the General Assembly) and to the number of symposia and meeting of Commissions held (see page 3 and 4).

3. On his proposal, the final *agenda* was approved in the form in which it will appear in these summary records. A *drafting Committee*, consisting of Messrs. AWBERY and BOUTRY, was appointed to draw up the resolutions in French and English.

Mr. C. J. GORTER, the Vice-President of the Union, took Professor KRAMERS' place in the Chair.

4. Mr FLEURY, the Secretary-General of the Union, reminded the meeting that, in preparation for the General Assembly, he had drafted a report¹ which had been circulated to National Committees the previous February.

He hoped that all delegates had been able to study it before-hand.

After drawing attention to various changes in the list of delegates previously distributed, and thanking the observers from other Unions for their presence at the General Assembly, Mr. FLEURY announced that the Executive Committee had favourably considered two preliminary applications for admission to membership of the Union from the physicists of Pakistan and Israel (applause).

He mentioned plans for the formation of two new Unions (for mathematics and bio-chemistry) which would probably apply for membership of the Council of Scientific Unions.

Although he did not wish to go into questions which were later to be discussed in detail by the Assembly, Mr. FLEURY reiterated that the rapid progress in the work of the Union, described in the President's address, had been possible only as a result of the help received from Unesco, the members of the Executive Committee, the physicists who had organized symposia, the Rapporteurs of Commissions and the Secretaries of National Committees, and of the efficient work of Professor KRAMERS himself.

On the proposal of Mr. GORTER, the Secretary General's report was unanimously approved (applause).

5. Mr. FLEURY reported on the work and future plans of the *International Commission on Optics* (see pages 15 and 16). The Assembly expressed approval of that Commission's activities.

6. Before the Assembly took up the discussion of the work and plans of the Commissions, the Secretary-General pointed out that it would be necessary to decide whether it was advisable to keep them in being and, if so, to appoint successors to some of their members. Delegations were asked to submit suggestions to the Secretariat as early as possible, so that the Executive Committee might submit proposals to the Assembly at its last meeting.

a) Mr. de BOER presented the report of the S. U. N. Commission (document S. U. N. 51-1) which had been circulated to the National Committees. After Mr. FLEURY had spoken, drawing attention to the activities of the S. U. N. Commission and the importance of its work, the report was approved. The new proposals from this Commission were to be discussed later (see below paragraphs 11 b and 19).

b) Mr. PRIGOGINE, the Secretary of the *Commission on Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics*, reported on that Commission's work (see page 8). No comments.

¹ Document SG. 51-2. The contents of the report are incorporated in various paragraphs of this pamphlet.

c) Mr. AMALDI referred to the questions studied by the Commission on *Cosmic Rays* (see page 8).

A scheme relating to a journal on high altitude research, put forward by biologists and physiologists, appeared to be of less interest to physicists.

The President observed that there was a Joint Commission competent to discuss that question.

d) A report by Mr. GORTER, the Secretary of the Commission on *Very Low Temperatures*, had recently been circulated (document T. B. T. 51-1; see below, page 9). Mr. SIMON, the Chairman of the Commission, gave some particulars about the meeting to be held in Oxford the following August and about the contacts established with the International Institute of Refrigeration.

The suggestions regarding the translation of Russian publications and « letters to the editor » were held over for later consideration after speeches by Mr. PERUCCA, Mr. AWBERY and Mr. FRASER (see page 9).

7. Mr. GORTER mentioned that a request for the establishment of an *Acoustics* Commission had been submitted to the Executive Committee. The Committee thought it undesirable that new Commissions should be set up except when they would clearly serve a useful purpose, but, in the instance in question, that condition seemed to be satisfied.

Following the advice of the British Committee, the Executive Committee proposed that, at least at the outset, the Commission should be of the « Specialized » type rather than a semi-independent « affiliated » body such as I. C. O.

Mr. KOSTEN agreed that the Commission should be small, but pointed out that the German Acoustics Society had recommended a larger membership. He thought that the new Commission would probably be interested in the recently founded Journal, *Acustica*.

Mr. SLATER reported that American acousticians, like these of other countries, were in favour of the proposed Commission.

It was then unanimously decided that a special Commission on Acoustics should be set up, with about 6 members. Mr. FLEURY asked these concerned to define its programme of work at the earliest possible date.

8. The Secretary-General announced that a request had been received from Mr. BAILLAUD, the President of the « Société Chronométrique » of France: arrangements were being made for the establishment of an *International Federation of Chronometry Associations*, which it was hoped might be affiliated to the Union of Pure and Applied Physics.

The work of this Federation would include the determination, measurement, conservation and diffusion of time and the measurement of its derivated quantities (frequencies, velocities, acceleration).

After speeches from Messrs. AWBERY, GORTER, DARROW, THOMSON and PÉRARD, recognizing that the Union was interested in applied physics, but pointing out that the proposed Federation so far included very few countries (France, Switzerland, United Kingdom), the Assembly resolved not to exclude the possibility of the affiliation of the Federation, in spite of its differences from other bodies already members of the Union. No firm decision could, however, be taken until further information was available.

9. *Joint Commissions.* Dr. FRASER gave particulars of the proposed new regulations

regarding such Commissions; their terms of reference were in future to be subject to renewal or suspension every three years.

a) The report of the *Commission on Spectroscopy*, which held its first meeting in September 1950 (see p. 13) was submitted by Professor BAKKER and approved without discussion.

b) Professor BOUTRY referred to the parallel work of the Publications Commission of the Union of Physics, the Joint Commission on *Physics Abstracts*, and Unesco's Committee of Experts on the same subject (see document S. G. 51-8).

After a discussion, in which Messrs. EWALD, AWBERY, SIMON and de BOER took part, on publication questions raised by the Commission on Very Low Temperatures (see paragraph 6 d above), the meeting rose at 12.30 p. m.

Second Meeting, Thursday, 12 July.

The meeting opened at 2 p. m.

10. After welcoming Professor AUGER, the President, in preparation for the vote the following day, submitted to the Assembly the proposals put forward by the outgoing *Executive Committee* for the election of new members (see below, paragraph 17) Mr. GORTER then took Professor KRAMERS' place in the Chair for the meeting.

11. a) The Assembly continued its discussion of the work of *Commissions* Dr. E. HUTCHINSON reminded the meeting of Unesco's efforts to bring about improvements in the production and distribution of physics *abstracts*. He read out the following proposal, put forward by the United States Committee :

« It is proposed that I. U. P. A. P. endorse the proposal of the Unesco Committee on Physics Abstracting that an international abstracting service be established under the auspices of I. C. S. U. The essence of this proposal is that existing abstract journals such as *Physics Abstracts* and the *Bulletin Analytique* would, under I. C. S. U. sponsorship, begin to co-operate in providing, each in its own language, abstracts having a wide coverage of all physics journals and with a minimum time delay between appearance of the article and of its abstract. It would be expected that this co-operation would be extended to abstract journals now existing or being planned in other languages. Eventually a truly international abstract service would be established with editions in each of the major languages in which physics research papers are written. »

It was decided that Dr. DARROW and the Drafting Committee should suggest a text combining the above proposal with the resolutions of the Commission on Abstracts (see page 14).

b) *S. U. N. Commission* (continuation). In connexion with resolution 1 (see page 7), Mr. WHEELER remarked that in the United States of America the word « billion » was generally employed in the sense of 10^9 ; Mr. PÉRARD and Mr. de BOER replied that it had in fact been recommended that, in order to avoid confusion, the term in questions should no longer be employed. Resolution 1 was unanimously adopted.

The Assembly then discussed the first draft of resolution 2 (numerals attached to symbols for chemical elements) and 3 (nuclide) after comments by Messrs. BARTON, de BOER, PÉRARD, GUGGENHEIM and AWBERY; it was decided that the wording of the resolutions should be reconsidered at a meeting of the S. U. N. Commission, which all those concerned were invited to attend.

Resolution 4 (practical system of units) and 5 (basing of the C. G. S. *e* and C. G. S. *m*-systems on 4 main units) were then unanimously adopted, after various comments had been made.

c) Mr. JACOBSEN submitted a report on the work of the Joint Commission on Radioactivity (see p. 11), which was approved without discussion.

Mr. FLEURY and Mr. FRASER announced that the Commission on *Physico-Chemical Data* was to meet in New-York during the forthcoming conference of the Union of Chemistry, and that the Joint Commission on Rheology proposed to convert itself into a Federation of Rheological Societies, to be affiliated to the Union of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics.

Dr. SLATER then submitted a report by Dr. BRODE on the Joint Commission on High Altitude Research Stations (see p. 13); no observations.

d) It had been proposed that the Joint Commission on the *Ionosphere* should be converted into a Commission on the polar year or, alternatively, that its scope of activity should be enlarged to take in the latter subject.

After speeches by Messrs. FRASER, MASSEY, EWALD and SLATER, the Assembly decided in favour of keeping the Commission in its existing form.

The Secretary-General then reported on the particulars received about the Joint Commissions on Radiobiology and Radiometeorology and the Commission on Macromolecules of the Union of Chemistry (from which Mr. HULTHEN wished to resign).

Mr. GORTER recalled that the principle of replacing some of the members of Commissions had been accepted, and that the Executive Committee had asked delegates to the Assembly to submit suggestions for that purpose.

12. *Travelling fellowships.* The Secretary-General stated that the Executive Committee had allotted the remaining balance of the subventions received from Unesco for that object (see page 4).

Information regarding the procedure to be followed in future by applicants for such fellowships was to be supplied as soon as possible.

13. *Forthcoming symposia.* The Secretary-General reminded members that a symposium on very low temperatures was to be held in Oxford from 22 to 30 August 1951, presided over by Professors SIMON and GORTER, as previously decided by the Executive Committee. The following programme subject to revision by the Executive Committee, having regard to the funds available and information received from local Committees) was submitted to the Assembly :

1952 (September or October) : Structure and properties of solid surfaces (Chicago). — Spectroscopy of γ and β rays (Amsterdam). — Thermodynamics of phase transitions (Paris). — Connexion between optics and the study of short waves (or another optics subject) (place to be fixed).

1953 and 1954 : Nuclear physics (Italie). — Physiological optics in relation to instrumental optics (Spain?). — Fundamental theoretical problems (Kyoto). — Thin films (Bristol). — Acoustics (place to be fixed). — Spectroscopy (place to be fixed).

Sir G. THOMSON mentioned the possibility of a symposium on thin films to be organized in Bristol in 1953 by Professor MOTT.

Mr. SLATER read a letter received from the Institute for the Study of Metals (Chicago) on the subject of the symposium on solid surfaces, and Mr. PRIGOGINE gave some further details about the proposed symposium on thermodynamics.

Dr. KOTANI then presented the invitation from the Japanese Committee (applause). Mr. MASSEY laid stress on the remarkable work being done in Japan (applause).

The Assembly agreed that the Union should, if appropriate, sponsor these various projects.

14. A proposal for the establishment of a *Joint Commission on the solid state* was submitted by Mr. EWALD; the proposal had been put forward by the Union of Crystallography, which would appoint 3 delegates to serve on the Commission; the Union of Pure and Applied Physics, as the parent Union, would also have 3 delegates on the Commission.

The Assembly approved the proposal.

Third Meeting, Friday, 13 July.

The meeting opened at 1. 30 p. m., with Professor KRAMERS in the Chair.

15. *International Laboratory for Nuclear Physics.* The scheme for such a laboratory first been submitted in 1950 by Professor I. I. RABI, a delegate of the United States of America, to the General Conference of Unesco, which had decided that the scheme would be further studied. A preliminary report, drawn up by Mr. E. AMALDI at the request of the Executive Committee of the Union of Physics, had been communicated to the members of the General Assembly.

Professor AUGER supplied some additional information the laboratory equipment, which would include an accelerator capable of several « giga electron volts » (10^9 eV), would be assembled in stages. A conference of experts had already been held, and the scientific Unions and States concerned would be convened to a meeting in Unesco House in the following November or December. A report on the progress so far achieved was to be published in the near future.

16. *Communications from the Secretary General.*

a) Mr. FLEURY, with the backing of the President, pointed out that the satisfactory progress of the Union's work was possible only if there was an organized Secretariat in each National Committee to transmit information from the Union to physicists in the country concerned and vice-versa. The services of the publishers of journals such as « Physics Today », who had agreed to publish regularly communications transmitted by the National Committee of their country, were specially acknowledged.

b) *The Directory of Physics Societies* (provisional edition) was submitted to the Assembly; the Secretariat asked for any necessary corrections and additional information to be sent in, with a view to the publication of a printed version.

c) Professor AUGER and the Secretary-General drew attention to an important point: as Unesco's subventions could be granted only as a partial contribution to the Unions, it was most desirable that the contributions to international co-operation in physics made by each country should be emphasized; on the average, these contributions were considerably higher but did not appear in the budget of the Union; they consisted in arrangements for scientists' travel or reception, time devoted to the writing of reports and the organizing of meetings, publications, etc. National Committees or bodies acting in their place were once more urged to supply the fullest possible information on that subject.

17. *Financial questions.* Mr. BAUER submitted the report of the Finance Commission (see above, page 16).

The Union's accounts showed a satisfactory state of affairs and were unanimously approved by the Assembly.

No increase in the rate of subscriptions was proposed for the time being, though it might become necessary in the future.

18. *Elections.* The Executive Committee's proposals, submitted by Professor KRAMERS, for the election of the new President, Vice-Presidents, Secretary-General and members of Commissions, as shown on pages 6 to 15 of this document, were unanimously adopted one by one (applause).

19. The final wording of the recommendations regarding the work of the Publications Commission and of the Joint Commission on Abstracts (see page 14) were adopted; recommendations 2 and 3 of the S. U. N. Commission (see page 7) were also adopted after the meeting had considered the comments submitted by Mr. de BOER.

Recommendation 6 of the S. U. N. Commission, concerning a Joint Committee to be formed with the International Electrotechnical Commission and « rationalization » questions was adopted (see page 8).

Mr. de BOER and Mr. PÉRARD then announced that a second list of recommended symbols had been drawn up, after detailed discussion, by the S. U. N. Commission. The list was not examined by the Assembly, but its publication was authorized.

20. *Other questions, votes of thanks.*

a) Various amendments to the Constitution, suggested mainly by Messrs. K. K. DARROW, P. P. EWALD and B. GROSS, were referred to the Executive Committee for study and possible submission to the General Assembly at its next session.

b) In reply to remarks by Pr. PÉRARD, the Secretary-General described the steps taken to ensure the widest possible participation in the work of the Union.

c) The following motion, prepared by Professor P. P. EWALD, was unanimously adopted :

« At the close of the General Assembly of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics, following an inspiring Symposium in Niels BOHR's Institute on « the principles of quantum Physics », attended by participants from all over the world, the General Assembly wishes to express most sincere thanks for generous financial help from U. N. E. S. C. O., without which neither of the meetings would have been nearly so successful. »

d) Mr. PÉRARD, being, to the best of his knowledge, the senior delegate present, expressed the meeting's warmest thanks to the two Presidents, Professor KRAMERS and Mr. GORTER, and to the Secretary General, for their conduct of the Assembly's business.

Professor KRAMERS endorsed the expression of thanks to Mr. GORTER and Mr. FLEURY, and also mentioned the invaluable assistance received from Mr. AWBERY and Mr. BOUTRY in the translation and drafting of the resolution (applause).

He asked Professor NIELSEN to transmit to the Danish Academy of Science the heartfelt thanks of the members of the Assembly for the welcome they had been given (applause).

Professor FLEURY wished to express his own and the Union's appreciation of the tact and efficiency with which Professor KRAMERS had carried out his functions as President, and of the sound judgment which he would still be placing at their disposal in the future (loud applause).

ANNEX I

Statutes

(Endorsed by the General Assembly in 1931 and amended by the General Assembly
in 1948.)
(See french text. p. 23).

ANNEX II

Documents published by the Union from 1949 to 1951.

(See french text p. 32.)

(For precedent publications, see document U. I. P.-1, p. 23-25 et U. I. P.-2, p. 23-25.)
